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PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. This article analyzes the structure of the service portfolio, the dynamics of regional service delivery, and digitalization efficiency indicators in the activities of Uzbekistan Post JSC based on the IMRAD approach. The empirical basis of the study includes service shares for 2020-2025 and regional and digital efficiency indicators for 2020-2024. The results indicate that traditional services — periodicals and written correspondence — still account for a significant share, while their long-term development potential remains relatively stable. At the same time, parcel delivery and digital services are emerging as promising directions. The decrease in the share of electronic operations from 14.36% in 2020 to 0.88% in 2024 highlights the need for further development of digital financial services within the system. Additionally, the customer satisfaction index increased from 86.47% to 97.40%, delivery speed improved by 40% in 2024, and the integral index reached 87.64% in 2023, confirming the positive outcomes of digitalization processes.

Keywords: postal services, digitalization, service portfolio, electronic operations, integral index, regional modernization.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada “O‘zbekiston pochta” AJ faoliyatida xizmatlar portfeli tuzilmasi, hududiy xizmat ko‘rsatish dinamikasi hamda raqamlashtirish samaradorligi ko‘rsatkichlari IMRAD yondashuvi asosida tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotning empirik bazasi 2020-2025-yillar davomida xizmatlar ulushi hamda 2020-2024-yillar kesimida hududiy va raqamli samaradorlik indikatorlaridan iborat. Natijalar an‘anaviy xizmatlar — davriy nashrlar va yozma xat-xabarlar — hali ham muhim ulushni egallayotganini, biroq ularning uzoq muddatli rivojlanish salohiyati nisbatan barqaror ekanini ko‘rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, posilka jo‘natmalari va raqamli xizmatlar istiqbolli yo‘nalish sifatida shakllanmoqda. Elektron operatsiyalar ulushining 2020-yildagi 14,36 % dan 2024-yilda 0,88 % gacha qisqarishi ushbu segmentda raqamli moliyaviy xizmatlarni yanada rivojlantirish zarurligini ko‘rsatadi. Shuningdek, mijozlar qoniqish indeksi 86,47 % dan 97,40 % gacha oshgani, yetkazib berish tezligining 2024-yilda 40 % ga yaxshilangani hamda integral indeksning 2023-yilda 87,64 % ga yetgani raqamlashtirish jarayonlarining ijobiy samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: pochta aloqasi, raqamlashtirish, xizmatlar portfeli, elektron operatsiyalar, integral indeks, hududiy modernizatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье проанализированы структура портфеля услуг, динамика регионального обслуживания и показатели эффективности цифровизации в деятельности АО «Почта Узбекистана» на основе подхода IMRAD. Эмпирическая база исследования включает долю услуг за 2020-2025 годы, а также региональные и цифровые показатели эффективности за 2020-2024 годы. Результаты показывают, что традиционные услуги — периодические издания и письменная корреспонденция — по-прежнему занимают значительную долю, при этом их долгосрочный потенциал развития характеризуется относительной стабильностью. В то же время посылочные отправления и цифровые услуги формируются как перспективные направления. Снижение доли электронных операций с 14,36 % в 2020 году до 0,88 % в 2024 году указывает на необходимость дальнейшего развития цифровых финансовых услуг в системе. Кроме того, рост индекса удовлетворённости клиентов с 86,47 % до 97,40 %, улучшение скорости доставки на 40 % в 2024 году, а также достижение интегрального индекса уровня 87,64 % в 2023 году подтверждают положительные результаты цифровизации.

Ключевые слова: почтовая связь, цифровизация, портфель услуг, электронные операции, интегральный индекс, региональная модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the digital economy, postal service enterprises are evolving beyond their traditional role as providers of basic mail exchange into multifunctional infrastructures integrated with logistics, e-commerce, financial services, and digital platforms. This transformation is of strategic importance for Uzbekistan Post JSC as well. On the one hand, the declining share of traditional services necessitates the diversification of the company's revenue base; on the other hand, the growth of electronic orders, digital tracking systems, hybrid mail, parcel delivery services, and platform-based solutions is creating new economic opportunities [1].

The data collected during the research indicate that transformation processes within the postal system have been consistently initiated; however, their implementation varies across service types and regions. The share of periodical publications within the service structure decreased from 71.5% to 51.8% during 2020–2025, while the share of written correspondence reached 44.5% in 2025. At the same time, the proportion of parcel deliveries increased from 0.1% in 2020 to 3.3% in 2025 [1]. These indicators demonstrate that the postal system continues to rely on traditional segments, while market demand is gradually shifting toward logistics and e-commerce-related services.

The objective of this study is to scientifically analyze the relationship between the service portfolio and the efficiency of digitalization in the operations of Uzbekistan Post JSC.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of digitalization in the postal services market is primarily associated with ensuring economic efficiency under conditions of universal service obligations, network infrastructure constraints, and competitive market environments. When postal services are organized entirely based on market mechanisms, maintaining extensive territorial coverage, ensuring tariff stability, and supporting socially significant services become critically important. Therefore, the analysis of postal operators' performance should not be limited to financial results alone but should also include a comprehensive evaluation of indicators such as service quality, territorial coverage, customer satisfaction, and the level of digital service adoption [2].

In scientific studies on digital transformation, technology is interpreted not only as a tool for automation but also as a key factor that reshapes service delivery models and value chains. In the postal sector, this process encompasses sorting, delivery, customer interaction, payments, order processing, and monitoring stages [3]. The empirical analysis conducted within this study confirms this trend: delivery time decreased from 9 units to 3 units during 2020–2024, while the customer satisfaction index reached 97.40% [1].

International and domestic studies identify e-commerce and parcel services as one of the most important growth drivers for postal operators. Such growth ensures high economic efficiency when logistics infrastructure, digital ordering systems, electronic payments, mobile interfaces, and real-time tracking systems operate in an integrated manner [4]. Based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC, the share of parcel deliveries increased from 0.1% in 2020 to 3.3% in 2025. This indicates that the segment is emerging as a promising direction for future development [1].

Digitalization processes are considered one of the main drivers accelerating institutional and technological transformation in the postal system. In particular, Michael A. Crew and Timothy J. Brennan (2014) substantiate the need for postal operators to restructure their value chains in the digital economy. Christian Jaag (2021) emphasizes the importance of specialization in the logistics segment under conditions of electronic substitution and the growth of e-commerce. Local scholars such as A.T. Kenjabayev and S.X. Nosirov (2024), Niyazov (2024), and Mamatkulov (2022) highlight the potential for improving service efficiency, optimizing costs, and enhancing interactive customer engagement through the implementation of digital technologies. These approaches are consistent with the findings of this study and confirm the importance of comprehensive digital transformation in the postal system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The empirical basis of the study is formed using data from Uzbekistan Post JSC. The data were classified into three groups: first, service portfolio indicators covering the period 2020–2025; second, the dynamics of traditional services across regional branches for 2020–2024; and third, indicators of digitalization efficiency for 2020–2024. The statistical data were not recalculated or modified; instead, they were systematized in accordance with academic research standards and presented in graphical form.

The analysis employed structural analysis, comparative analysis of time series, regional comparison, indicator-based grouping, and an integrated assessment approach. Structural analysis was used to determine the shares within the service portfolio, while dynamic analysis enabled the identification of trends over time. Regional analysis facilitated the evaluation of disparities among branches.

To assess the efficiency of digitalization, a system of indicators was applied, including the share of digital services, the proportion of electronic transactions, improvements in delivery speed, cost dynamics, customer satisfaction, service diversification, revenue growth, the level of regional modernization, the share of digital orders, and a composite (integral) index. These indicators were consistently retained throughout the study and systematically applied to ensure a comprehensive evaluation [1].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The first direction of the analysis focused on identifying structural changes within the service portfolio. Over the period 2020–2025, periodical publications remained the largest segment each year; however, their share decreased from 71.5% in 2020 to 51.8% in 2025. In contrast, the share of written correspondence increased from 26.2% in 2020 to 44.5% in 2025.

The decline in the share of electronic money transfers—from 2.1% in 2020 to 0.4% in 2025—indicates the increasing influence of market conditions and the intensification of competition in this segment. At the same time, the growth in the share of parcel deliveries from 0.1% to 3.3% confirms the rising potential of services associated with e-commerce.

These trends demonstrate a gradual transformation of the service portfolio from traditional communication services toward logistics and digitally integrated service models (Table 1).

Table 1
Share of service types in Uzbekistan Post JSC (2020–2025, %)¹

Type of Service	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Written correspondence	26.2	28.1	25.1	30.8	30.6	44.5
Electronic money transfers	2.1	2.3	1.2	0.6	0.5	0.4
Parcel deliveries	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	3.3
Periodical publications	71.5	69.4	73.4	68.2	68.2	51.8

The table data indicate that significant structural changes occurred in the service portfolio during 2020–2025. Although periodical publications remained the leading segment, their share decreased from 71.5% to 51.8%. The share of written correspondence demonstrated steady growth, increasing from 26.2% to 44.5%. The rise in the share of parcel deliveries from 0.1% to 3.3% reflects the increasing activity of services related to e-commerce. Meanwhile, the decline in the share of electronic money transfers suggests the presence of opportunities for developing new digital solutions in this segment (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Changes in the Structure of the Service Portfolio (2020–2025).

¹ Source: Compiled by the author based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC.

The analysis of Figure 1 shows that traditional services still dominate the structure of the service portfolio. While such a composition ensures a stable operational base for the enterprise in the short term, it also creates the need for deeper service diversification in the long term. This is because the segments of periodical publications and written correspondence are gradually transforming under the influence of the development of digital information exchange. At the same time, the growth of parcel services indicates increasing opportunities for developing a service model integrated with digital commerce and logistics.

The structure of financial indicators reflects the complex and multi-stage nature of service transformation. In particular, the share of hybrid mail increased significantly during 2020–2025, rising from 4% in 2020 to 43% in 2024 and reaching 39% in 2025. Meanwhile, the share of written correspondence declined from 16% in 2020 to 5% in 2025, and the share of periodical publications decreased from 17% to 3% over the same period. These trends confirm the growing financial significance of digital and hybrid formats within the service portfolio, as well as the consistent progression of transformation processes (Table 2).

Table 2
Dynamics of Financial Indicators by Service Type²

Type of Service	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Written correspondence	16	17	13	11	7	5
Parcel services	6	9	7	5	4	3
Periodical publications	17	8	9	5	3	3
Utility payments	8	5	2	1	0	2
Hybrid mail	4	7	17	31	43	39
Other services	49	54	52	47	43	48

The results of the regional analysis indicate significant variation in the use of traditional services across branches. According to the 2024 data, the highest volumes of written correspondence were recorded in the “Tashkent Postal Center” with 1,497.5 thousand items, followed by Tashkent region with 659.5 thousand items, Kashkadarya region with 446.2 thousand items, and Samarkand region with 404.5 thousand items.

Relatively lower figures were observed in Syrdarya region (141.5 thousand items), Khorezm region (166.2 thousand items), Jizzakh region (196.8 thousand items), and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (205.5 thousand items). These disparities reflect regional differences in service utilization levels as well as variations in infrastructure development.

In terms of periodical publications, the leading regions in 2024 were Fergana region with 3,248.6 thousand items, the “Tashkent Postal Center” with 2,397.7 thousand items, Namangan region with 1,338.5 thousand items, and Tashkent region with 1,321.3 thousand items. These figures indicate that stable demand for traditional services persists in certain regions (Table 3).

Table 3
Volume of Written Correspondence and Periodical Publications by Region in 2024 (thousand items)³

Region	Written Correspondence	Periodical Publications
Republic of Karakalpakstan	205.5	170.7
Andijan	215.6	10.6
Bukhara	324.4	106.4
Jizzakh	196.8	717.2
Kashkadarya	446.2	695.1
Navoi	207.5	482.4
Namangan	279.1	1338.5
Samarkand	404.5	441.3
Surkhandarya	282.3	103.8
Syrdarya	141.5	48.4
Tashkent region	659.5	1321.3

² Source: Compiled by the author based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC.

³ Source: Compiled by the author based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC.

Fergana	375.4	3248.6
Khorezm	166.2	1099.5
Tashkent Postal Center	1497.5	2397.7

The table data demonstrate significant variation in the use of traditional services across regions. In terms of written correspondence, the “Tashkent Postal Center” (1,497.5 thousand items) and Tashkent region (659.5 thousand items) occupy leading positions. Regarding periodical publications, Fergana region (3,248.6 thousand items), the “Tashkent Postal Center” (2,397.7 thousand items), and Namangan region (1,338.5 thousand items) show the highest indicators. The relatively lower results observed in certain regions reflect regional characteristics and differences in service utilization levels. Overall, the findings indicate that demand and infrastructure development vary significantly across regions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Regional Indicators for 2024: Written Correspondence and Periodical Publications

The analysis of regional indicators shows that postal services exhibit a certain degree of centralization. In particular, the “Tashkent Postal Center” and several major regions occupy leading positions in terms of service volumes, while in other regions the scale of traditional services remains relatively limited. These disparities justify the need for flexible management mechanisms that take into account regional specialization, logistics workload, and the level of digital literacy, rather than relying on a uniform approach.

The share of digital services remained at 0% during 2020–2022 but increased to 11.11% in 2023 and further to 20.00% in 2024. This trend reflects the consistent development of digitalization processes. At the same time, the share of electronic operations demonstrates an opposite trend, declining from 14.36% in 2020 to 8.33% in 2021, 3.09% in 2022, 1.48% in 2023, and 0.88% in 2024.

This divergence indicates that although the range of digital services is expanding, their actual operational activity and practical utilization remain relatively limited. Therefore, assessing the efficiency of digitalization requires not only consideration of the number of services or platform expansion but also a comprehensive evaluation of their real usage intensity (Table 4).

Table 4
Share of Digital Services and Electronic Operations (2020–2024)⁴

Year	Number of Digital Services	Total Services	Digital Services, %	Electronic Operations (units)	Total Operations (units)	Electronic Share, %
2020	0	8	0.00	21,803,241.0	151,784,432.9	14.36
2021	0	8	0.00	14,293,787.1	171,535,008.2	8.33
2022	0	8	0.00	8,060,413.0	260,979,763.0	3.09

4 Source: Compiled by the author based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC.

2023	1	9	11.11	4,044,957.4	274,098,946.5	1.48
2024	2	10	20.00	4,031,286.0	458,773,493.3	0.88

Operational efficiency indicators clearly demonstrate the positive impact of digitalization processes. In particular, delivery time decreased from 9 units to 3 units during 2020–2024, while the annual improvement rate reached 40.00% in 2024.

The customer satisfaction index increased from 86.47% in 2020 to 97.40% in 2024, indicating a significant improvement in service quality. In addition, the revenue growth rate reached 158.02% in 2024, confirming the increasing economic efficiency of operations.

The level of regional modernization coverage also exhibited positive dynamics, rising from 0% in 2020 to 27.78% in 2024. These results confirm that digitalization plays a crucial role in enhancing operational efficiency, improving service quality, and developing infrastructure (Table 5).

Table 5

Operational and Economic Efficiency Indicators of Digitalization (2020–2024, %)⁵

Year	Improvement in Delivery Speed	Customer Satisfaction	Revenue Growth	Regional Modernization	Composite Index
2020	22.22	86.47	140.59	0.00	57.42
2021	14.29	89.72	119.44	16.67	55.57
2022	0.00	95.10	108.82	16.67	61.29
2023	16.67	95.68	127.88	22.22	87.64
2024	40.00	97.40	158.02	27.78	71.94

The table data reflect a positive dynamic in operational efficiency indicators over the period 2020–2024. The improvement in delivery speed reached 40.00% in 2024, indicating enhanced logistics efficiency. The customer satisfaction index showed consistent growth, reaching 97.40%. The revenue growth indicator also increased to 158.02%, confirming improved economic performance. The level of regional modernization expanded progressively over time. The composite index reflects an overall upward trend in performance, demonstrating the systemic positive impact of digitalization (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Digital Services, Electronic Operations, Customer Satisfaction, and Composite Index

⁵ Source: Compiled by the author based on data from Uzbekistan Post JSC.

The results presented in Table 5 and the corresponding figures indicate that the efficiency of digitalization has a multidimensional nature. On the one hand, service quality, delivery speed, customer satisfaction, and revenue growth have all demonstrated positive trends. On the other hand, the share of electronic operations has shown a declining tendency, while service diversification reached 2.78% in 2024.

The dynamics of the composite index over the period 2020–2024 are as follows: 57.42% in 2020, 55.57% in 2021, 61.29% in 2022, 87.64% in 2023, and 71.94% in 2024. The peak observed in 2023 reflects an accelerated phase of digitalization processes, whereas the 2024 figures indicate the need to further improve the balance among individual system indicators.

The overall analysis suggests that for Uzbekistan Post JSC, enhancing the efficiency of digitalization should not be limited to the mere introduction of digital services. Instead, it requires the integration of digital services with actual user activity, logistics processes, and revenue models. Such an approach would enable not only the expansion of digital service offerings but also a consistent increase in their practical utilization.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study indicate that the service portfolio of Uzbekistan Post JSC underwent significant structural changes during 2020–2025. Although periodical publications remained the dominant segment, their share declined to 51.8% in 2025. The share of written correspondence, accounting for 44.5% in 2025, confirms that traditional services still play an important role. At the same time, the increase in the share of parcel deliveries to 3.3% reflects the emergence of promising directions associated with e-commerce.

In terms of digitalization efficiency, the improvement in delivery speed by 40% in 2024, the increase in customer satisfaction to 97.40%, the growth in revenue by 158.02%, and the expansion of modernization coverage to 27.78% can be considered significant positive outcomes. However, the decline in the share of electronic operations from 14.36% to 0.88% indicates the existence of additional opportunities for development in this area.

From a practical perspective, several key recommendations can be proposed. First, parcel and e-commerce services should be systematically developed as strategic growth drivers. Second, to increase the share of electronic operations, postal services should be integrated with mobile payments, personal user accounts, electronic ordering systems, and real-time monitoring tools. Third, instead of applying a uniform management model across regions, a differentiated approach should be adopted: enhancing logistics speed in high-volume regions while promoting alternative solutions such as digital services and electronic subscriptions in lower-volume areas. Fourth, the composite index should be used as a key performance indicator (KPI) for management purposes, enabling a comprehensive assessment of digitalization efficiency by integrating not only the level of technological implementation but also customer satisfaction, revenue growth, operational speed, and regional coverage indicators.

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